

Definitions List for Data Management Regulations Leiden University 2021

Version 1.0; 26 January 2022

*This document contains working definitions for the purpose of the Leiden University
Data Management Regulations [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5825356>]
For more information and support: [Research Support Portal](#)*

Certified repository (Trusted Digital Repository)

A data repository is an archive for research data. A trusted digital repository is a digital archive whose mission is to store, manage and provide reliable, long-term access to digital resources and it has been certified by an official organisation. A well-known certification for data repositories is Core Trust Seal.¹

Copyrights

In many cases research data are not protected by copyright. Only research data that qualify as original work are protected by copyright. Collaboration or consortium agreements, user rights, data user agreements or licenses are used to define what others are allowed to do with research data.

Data Management Plan (DMP)

A formal statement describing how research data will be managed and documented throughout a research project and the terms regarding the subsequent deposit of the data with a data repository for long-term management and preservation.²

Data protocol

The data protocol is the elaboration of the Data Management Regulations at the level of the faculties or the research institutes.

FAIR principles

FAIR refers to 15 principles on how to manage research data in such a way that they are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.³

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):

European regulation with rules for processing personal data. In Dutch: Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG).

¹ Source: Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed <https://lerenpreserveren.nl/woordenlijst/trusted-digital-repository/>

² Source: CASRAI Research Data Management Glossary <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary/>

³ Source: <https://www.library.universiteitleiden.nl/researchers/data-management/fair-data>

Metadata

Standardised structured information explaining data items like, but not limited to: purpose, origin, time references, geographic location, creator, access conditions and terms of use of a data collection. Documentation and explanation of the data.⁴

Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity

The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity lays down the five basic principles of academic research,: honesty, scrupulousness, transparency, independence, responsibility.⁵

Non-digital research data

Non-digital research data can differ from one discipline to the other: think of bio samples, archaeological findings, paper questionnaires or consent forms. The faculty or institute's data protocol will contain guidelines on how to keep, document, archive or destroy non-digital data.

Personal data

Personal data refer to any information that can be traced back to a person. This information could be a name, address or location, but it could also be bank account numbers, telephone numbers or post codes with house numbers.

Sensitive information, such as someone's race, religion or health, is called extraordinary personal data. These data have an extra layer of legal protection.⁶

Research data

The recorded factual material commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate research findings.⁷

Research Data Management

Research data management is an integral part of the research process, which concerns the way you collect, analyze, store, share, archive and publish research data, to satisfy the needs of current and future data users.⁸

Scientific publication

All publications that present results from scientific research.

Secure handling of research data

The University has guidelines for working securely online in order to guarantee the availability, integrity and confidentiality of sensitive information.⁹

⁴ Source: LCRDM: <https://www.lcrdm.nl/begrippenlijst>

⁵ Source: <https://www.staff.universiteitleiden.nl/research/quality-and-integrity/academic-integrity/academic-integrity>

⁶ Source: <https://www.staff.universiteitleiden.nl/ict/privacy-and-data-protection/personal-data/personal-data>

⁷ Source: LCRDM: <https://www.lcrdm.nl/en/glossary>; see also: <https://casrai.org/rdm-glossary>

⁸ Source: LCRDM <https://www.lcrdm.nl/en/glossary>

⁹ Source: <https://www.staff.universiteitleiden.nl/ict/privacy-and-data-protection/working-securely-online>

Sustainable storage (long-term preservation)

Refers to the series of managed activities necessary to ensure continued access to digital materials for as long as necessary.¹⁰

Terms for storage, preservation and deletion

Research data must be kept for at least ten years unless other rules apply. Medical data should be kept for at least 15 years, personal data should be deleted when no longer necessary for the purpose for which they are collected.

¹⁰ Source: <https://www.dpconline.org/handbook/glossary#D>

